

PRINCIPLES OF GOOD OPEN SCIENCE

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Opening Up Open Science: Innovations, Ideas and Possibilities

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1) Good Open Science is a means, it is not an end in itself (OECD 2015)

- Don't make Open Science into a fetish or ideology
- Open Science needs to be understood and assessed as part of a broader perspective on the relationship between science and society

Good Open Science tries to make sure that OS accomplishes its primary aims: fostering good research and increasing its impact on society.

2) Good Open Science supports good research and innovation

- It should facilitate communication between scientists and increase the efficiency of research
- It enhances the efficiency, quality and integrity of research (e.g. by facilitating replicability, but also avoiding unnecessary duplication)
- Good Open Science is fair and supports ethical research
- It supports publication of negative research results
- It uses FAIR principles for Open Data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)
- Good Open Science uses the full potential of new technologies (e.g. the right to machine-read or data-mine), and does not create new artificial barriers

3) Good Open Science is a public good

- Good Open Science is freely and universally accessible.
- Good Open Science belongs to the community (as opposed to most knowledge generated by industry science)
- Public/private partnerships can be beneficial, but we should avoid privatizing public goods.

- Good Open Science privileges a service model of scientific publishing and data management (ownership and copyright remains with authors or creative commons license; public right to data-mine or search with robots; metadata can be accessed and used)

4) With Good Open Science, no researcher is left behind

- In implementing OS, do not put the burden on the (already overextended) researcher: create enough structures of support and assistance so that all researchers can make their science open
- Open Science promotes the circulation of researchers without barriers
- No one size fits all
- OS policies and rules must not disenfranchise any group of scholars or depend on their affluence, and in particular not disadvantage younger scholars, scholars in LMIC countries, or scholars in "soft" disciplines with less available funding.
- Good Open Science is acting against or acting to avoid neo-colonial Open Science and extractive science from LMIC countries
- Good Open Science policy takes into account feedback from different actors - and in particular the different views of scientists – to optimize itself. Structures and policies should be flexible and adaptable, and researchers should be stimulated to use their creativity for developing new and better ways for advancing Good Open Science.

5) Good Open Science is embedded in a supportive research culture

- Collaboration should be valued, together with competition. (Open Access and Open Data tend to flourish in different research cultures)
- Credit (for data generation, for making data open, for research software development,...) and authorship should be fairly distributed.
- Evaluation is transparent and employs open and responsible metrics
- Openness exposes researchers to some vulnerability, which requires principles of 'fair play'.
- A supportive research culture also involves constructive criticism, safe spaces for exploratory research where there is place for failure, and acceptance of the messiness of science. This is needed to foster different aspects of Open Science (e.g. transparency, open notebook science, open peer review and open data).